

Supporting Information for

Sinusoidal Displacement Describes Disorder in CsPbBr₃ Nanocrystal**Superlattices**

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Figure S1. High-resolution STEM-HAADF (High-Angle Annular Dark Field) images of monolayers of (a),(b) 8nm-C₁₈ nanocrystals (well-separated from each other) and (c),(d) C₈ nanocrystals (some necking occurs under the imaging conditions).

Table S1. Superlattice periodicities from the GISAXS profiles (Figure 2f in the main text).

Sample	Periodicity [Å]		Crystal System	Space group
	Out-of-plane	In-plane		
C ₁₈ 5 nm	82.8 ± 0.8		Cubic	Pm-3m
C ₁₈ 8 nm			Cubic	Pm-3m
C ₁₂			Cubic	Pm-3m
C ₁₀			Cubic	Pm-3m
C ₈	136.8 ± 0.3	139.1 ± 0.3	Cubic	Pm-3m

Figure S2. High-resolution SEM images of superlattices assembled from (a) C₈-capped nanocrystals, (b) C₁₀-capped nanocrystals, (c) C₁₂-capped nanocrystals and (d) 8nm-C₁₈ nanocrystals.

Figure S3. (a) 001 GISAXS peak, (b) azimuthal broadening profile and Gaussian fitting, (c) radial broadening profile and Gaussian fitting. From top to bottom: 5nm-C₁₈, 8nm-C₁₈, C₁₂, C₁₀, and C₈ nanocrystal superlattice samples.

Figure S4. (a) 100 GISAXS peak, (b) azimuthal broadening profile and Gaussian fitting, (c) radial broadening profile and Gaussian fitting. From top to bottom: 5nm-C₁₈, 8nm-C₁₈, C₁₂, C₁₀, and C₈ nanocrystal superlattice samples.

Figure S5. GISAXS azimuthal broadening for in-plane (100) and out-of-plane (001) directions.

Figure S6. Comparison of the photoluminescence (PL) and absorption spectrum of C₁₂ and C₁₈ nanocrystals dispersed in toluene. The wider PL spectrum and less pronounced excitonic absorption peaks indicate a larger size dispersion for C₁₂ nanocrystals than for 8nm-C₁₈ nanocrystals. We hypothesize that the larger size dispersion of the C₁₂ sample leads to pronounced size selectivity and the presence of superlattices with different periodicities. This could further explain the large value of the radial broadening of the GISAXS peaks reported in Figure 2 of the main text for the C₁₂ sample. The enhanced size selectivity in nanocrystal superlattices with shorter ligands was reported previously.^[1]

Table S2. Multilayer diffraction fit results of GIWAXS patterns. Structure parameters extracted from the multilayer diffraction fits. The fits are shown in Figure S7. To account for the disordered contribution present in the C₈ GIWAXS pattern (Figure 3e), we subtracted a Gaussian background from the peak profile; the fitting results before and after subtraction are reported in *C₈ and C₈ rows, respectively. Parameters: d = nanocrystal lattice constant; L = interparticle distance (surface to surface); σ_L = stacking disorder; N = nanocrystal thickness; σ_N = nanocrystal thickness distribution, S – colloidal softness [calculated as L/(d·N)].

Sample	d [Å]	L [Å]	σ_L [Å]	N [planes]	σ_N [planes]	S = L/(d·N)
(001) Out-of-plane						
5nm-C₁₈	5.886	36.493	2.041	8.879	1.239	0.70
8nm-C₁₈	5.866	37.814	1.567	13.531	1.561	0.48
C₁₂	5.852	37.661	1.282	12.249	2.129	0.53
C₁₀	5.866	33.567	1.281	13.938	2.012	0.41
C₈	5.860	32.677	1.203	19.116	3.501	0.29
*C₈	5.858	32.677	1.325	19.212	2.872	0.29
(100) In-plane						
5nm-C₁₈	5.906	36.650	2.046	8.901	1.367	0.70
8nm-C₁₈	5.910	37.601	1.601	13.082	1.759	0.49
C₁₂	5.898	38.262	1.330	13.004	1.004	0.50
C₁₀	5.891	34.005	1.246	14.167	0.886	0.41
C₈	5.905	33.185	1.160	18.401	3.014	0.31
*C₈	5.909	33.126	1.31	18.343	3.504	0.31

Figure S7. Multilayer diffraction fits of GIWAXS patterns. a-f) Out-of-plane (001) (left) and in-plane (100) (right) diffraction profiles extracted from the 2D GIWAXS patterns reported in Figure 3. They correspond to (a) 5nm-C₁₈, (b) 8nm-C₁₈, (c) C₁₂, (d) C₁₀ and (e) C₈, and (f) *C₈.

Figure S8. Concentration-dependent C_8 superlattice order.

Figure S9. GISAXS C_8 fitting of the disordered component.

Figure S10. (a) 2D GIWAXS pattern of C₁₀ superlattice and (b) comparison between the 001 and 101 profiles extracted from (a) and the calculated diffraction patterns of C₁₀ superlattice with $\sigma_L \approx 1.28$ and 1.8 \AA .

Table S3. Multilayer diffraction fit results of Bragg patterns. Structure parameters extracted from the multilayer diffraction fits. Fits are shown in Figure S11.

Sample	d [Å]	L [Å]	σ_L [Å]	N [planes]	σ_N [planes]
(001) Out-of-plane					
5 nm-C ₁₈ NCs	5.879	36.483	2.040	8.831	1.366
8 nm-C ₁₈ NCs	5.828	36.359	1.510	12.743	1.998
C ₁₂	5.835	36.912	0.866	12.762	0.746
C ₁₀	5.808	32.905	0.958	13.778	0.573
C ₈	5.808	32.901	1.203	19.116	3.501
(101) Out-of-plane					
C ₁₀	4.108	26.477	1.853	≈16	n/a
C ₈	4.103	29.994	1.264	≈20	n/a

Figure S11. Multilayer diffraction fits of Bragg patterns. a-d) On the right are (001) out-of-plane peak profiles and on the left are (101) peak profiles extracted from the 2D GIWAXS patterns.

Figure S12. Simulated wide-angle X-ray diffraction patterns of CsPbBr₃ nanocrystal superlattices showing the effect of changing λ_l (longitudinal wavelength), A_l (longitudinal amplitude), λ_t (transversal wavelength) and A_t (transversal amplitude). The longitudinal parameter has little effect on the (101) peak, while it affects the broadening of the (001) and (002) peaks. As discussed in the main text, the broadening of the (101) peak is primarily influenced by the transversal parameters.

Figure S13. (a, b) Simulated wide-angle X-ray diffraction patterns of CsPbBr₃ nanocrystal superlattices showing the effect of changing A_t (transversal amplitude) and A_l (longitudinal amplitude) respectively (keeping constant the oscillation wavelengths $\lambda_t = 400$ nm and $\lambda_l = 200$ nm). These simulations explore the extreme regimes characterized by oscillations with zero amplitude (bottom pattern in (a)) or extremely large amplitudes (top patterns in (a) and (b)). (c) Illustration of the transversal (left) and longitudinal (right) spring constants, k_t and k_l . k_l describes the compressibility of ligands when nanocrystals are pushed towards each other, and k_t describes the shear when nanocrystals are sliding parallel to each other.